

**AORTOKORONAR SHUNTLASH O`TKAZGAN BEMORLARDA
INTERVENTSION AMALIYOT O`TKAZISH**

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Dolzarbli: Aorta koronar shuntlash amaliyotini o'tkazgandan bir necha yildan so'ng olib borilgan davo choralari qaramasdan bemorlarda nostabil stenokardiya belgilari qayta rivojlanish holatlari kuzatilyapti. Garchi hozirgi kunga kelib intervension kardiologiya sohasida samarali davo usullari aniqlangan bo'lsada, aortokoronar shuntlash amaliyoti (AKSH) o'tkazgan bemorlar uchun intervension amaliyot o'tqazish cheklanganligicha qolmoqda.

Tadqiqod maqsadi: Aorta koronar shuntlash amaliyoti va koronar intervension muolajalarni o'tkazgan bemorlarda angiografik o'zgarishlarini va amaliyotdan so'ng bemorlarning yashovchanligiga ta'sirini baholash.

Material va metodlar: 2010-yil yanvaridan 2020-yil dekabrigacha kardiologiya bo'limiga yotqizilgan 30 nafar Aorta koronar shuntlash amaliyoti va koronar intervension muolajalarni o'tkazgan bemorlarning kasallik tarixi retrospektiv taxlil qilindi. Arterial gipertenziya, giperlipedemiya, qandli diabet bo'lgan va chap qorincha zarb hajmi nisbatan past bemorlar tanlab olindi.

Natija: 2010 yildan 2020 yilgacha aorta koronar shuntlash amaliyoti o'tqazgan 15 nafar bemorga stent qo'yildi va 15 nafarida aorta koronar shuntlash amaliyoti o'tkazildi. Har 5 yillikda natijalar hisoblanganda amaliyotning muvaffaqiyatli o'tish ko'rsatkichi 2010-2015 yillarda 89% va 2015-2020 yillarda 91%, $P < 0,0001$ ni tashkil etdi va vaqt o'tishi bilan yaxshilanib bordi. Uzoq muddatli o'lim 2015 yilgacha bo'lgan guruhda (nisbiy xavf = 1,7, 94%) va 2020-yilgacha (nisbiy xavf = 1,6, 90%) amaliyot o'tkazgan bemorlarda nostabil stenokardiya xavfi rivojlanishiga nisbatan yuqori bo'lgan. O'lim, miokard infarkti, tomirlarda restenoz paydo bo'lish xavfining kamayishi stentlash amaliyoti bajarilgan guruhda (73 %) ikkinchi guruh bemorlarga (58%) nisbatan yuqori edi.

Xulosa: Olib borilgan tadqiqod natijalari shuni ko'rsatdiki, stentlash amaliyotini boshdan kechirgan bemorlarda revaskulizatsiyaning rivojlanish jarayoni, nostabil steniokardiya rivojlanishi va o'lim xavfining rivojlanishi aorta koronar shuntlash amaliyoti bajarilgan bemorlarga nisbatan bir muncha pastroq. Yillar davomida intervension kardiologiyadagi yutuqlar va uzoq muddatli o'lim xavfining kamayishi

bemor hayotining yaxshilanishiga, shuningdek, takroriy revaskulyarizatsiya uchrash ehtimolining kamayishiga olib keldi.

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